

Regioselective mononitration of coumarins using claycop reagent

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Abstract : Coumarins are nitrated by claycop (cupric nitrate impregnated on the K10 montmorillonite) in acetic anhydride at room temperature to give corresponding regioselective mononitro coumarins in good to excellent yields. Among the products three nitrocoumarins are new.

Keywords : Coumarin, claycop, nitration, acetic anhydride.

Introduction

A large number of coumarins occur in nature and some of them possess biological activities¹. Numerous nitrocoumarins exhibit biological properties² such as 3-nitrocoumarin is neutrotropic³, antioxidant⁴, antimicrobials, useful in the treatment of asthma, hayfever and rhinitis⁶ and 7-hydroxy-8-nitrocoumarin is cytotoxic⁷. Nitrocoumarins are also used as synthetic intermediates for the preparation of chromene derivatives⁸ and benzocoumarins⁹ and as dienophiles¹⁰ in Diels-Alder reaction.

Surface mediated organic reactions are undergoing extensive investigations especially because they are environment friendly. There has recently been an upsurge in interest in the use of supported reagents¹¹ and catalysts as the use of heterogeneous system makes the purification of the reaction products much simple and the spent reagent or the catalyst can be simply filtered off. The general characteristics of this type of chemical reactions are the low cost of the supported reagents, their often surprising reactivities and the ease with which the reaction is carried out. Much of the work till date uses acid activated clays as a support, which provides a high surface dispersal of the reagent. The use of heterogeneous system often results increased yields, higher product specificity and higher regio or stereo chemical selectivity as compared to the equivalent homogeneous systems¹².

Nitration of organic compounds with metal nitrates has been reported from time to time. Copper(II) nitrate was used for the nitration of acetophenone, chalcone and flavone¹³, thiophene¹⁴ and organosilicon compounds¹⁵. Recently novel reagents consisting of metallic nitrates impregnated on lamellar montmorillonite have got potential utility in organic synthesis such as clayfen and claycop. Claycop and clayfen are acid activated clay supported anhydrous copper(II) and iron(III) nitrate respectively. Claycop is used for aromatic nitration¹⁶, dimerisation¹⁷ and oxidation reactions¹⁸. Very few methods are reported in literature for the direct nitration of coumarins¹⁹⁻²¹. Those reported suffer from the drawbacks of longer reaction periods, polynitration, harsh acidic conditions, side reactions, low product yields and use of either toxic or expensive reagent. Hence we felt the need for the present work on nitration of coumarins.

Results and discussion

Our goal in undertaking this work was three-fold, (a) to overcome the limitations and drawbacks of the reported methods such as tedious work up, strongly acidic media, oxidation ability of the reagent and safety problems (storage, handling); (b) to reach a high yielding one-pot synthesis of mononitro phenol using a combination of reagent and (c) to consider the rules of green chemistry to implement nitration in eco-friendly conditions.

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In the present communication, we report a new practical route for the direct nitration of coumarins using claycop (copper nitrate impregnated on montmorillonite K10) in presence of acetic anhydride to give good yields of mononitro products. The nitration proceeds via *in situ* generation of 'acetyl nitrate' from cupric nitrate and acetic anhydride and which dissociates to give nitronium ion. The solvent by solvating the intermediate $\text{CH}_3\text{COONO}_2$, stabilized the charged NO_2^+ electrophile and hence reducing the activation energy. The two step mechanism can be shown as below :

1st step :

2nd step :

All these reactions take place on the surface of microporous solid clay montmorillonite K10 which has high diffusivity and shape selectivity. Partial dehydration in acetic anhydride activates copper(II) nitrate. These activated nitrate complexes, with covalent metal-ligand bonds, are stabilized in a convenient form by impregnation upon montmorillonite clay K10. Hence the reaction is regioselective and yields are good to excellent (Table 1). Among the products obtained three nitocoumarines **18**, **19** and **20** are new (Fig. 1). Their respective structures are confirmed by the spectral and analytical data.

Table 1. Nitration of coumarins

Reactant	Product ^a	Time (h)	Yield ^b (%)	M.p. (lit.) (°C)
1	10	2.0	70	192 (191) ²¹
2	11	1.0	45	218 (218) ²³
	12		40	245 (245) ²¹
3	13	1.0	40	263 (262) ²⁴
	14		38	255 (256) ²⁴
4	15	1.5	72	92 (90-92) ²¹
5	16	0.5	80	225 (225) ²¹
6	17	2.5	70	126 (125-127) ²¹
	18		47	282
7	19	2.0	36	228
	20		70	90
8	21	1.0	80	229 (229-231) ²⁵

^aProducts are characterized by physical and spectral data.

^bYields refer to isolated pure products.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Products are characterized by physical and spectral data. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer. Chemical shifts are given in ppm (δ) with respect to tetramethylsilane and coupling constant (J) is in Hz.

General procedure :

The claycop reagent was prepared²² as usual. To a solution of coumarin (**1**, 1 mmol, 146 mg) in acetic anhydride (25 ml) claycop (4 g) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously at room temperature for 2 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored on TLC plate (silica gel, benzene). After the completion of the reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was diluted with 100 ml of cold water and the mixture was extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml). The organic extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to give the crude solid which was purified by column chromatography to give yellow crystals of 8-nitrocoumarin (**10**) in 70% yield; m.p. 192 °C.

Spectral and analytical data :

7-Methoxy-4-methyl-6-nitrocoumarin (18) : ¹H NMR [(CD₃)₂CO, 90 MHz] : δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.1 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.0 (1H, s, C₈-H), 8.1 (1H, s, C₅-H); IR (KBr) : 880, 1365, 1500, 1700 cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 56.15; H, 3.80; N, 5.93. Calcd. for C₁₁H₉O₅N : C, 56.17; H, 3.82; N, 5.95%).

7-Methoxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin (19) : ¹H NMR [(CD₃)₂CO, 90 MHz] : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.6 (1H, s, C₃-H), 6.9 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, C₆-H), 7.4 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, C₅-H); IR (KBr) : 896, 1340, 1520, 1725 cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 56.15; H, 3.82; N, 5.92. Calcd. for C₁₁H₉O₅N : C, 56.17; H, 3.82; N, 5.95%).

7-Ethoxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin (20) : ¹H NMR [(CD₃)₂CO, 90 MHz] : δ 1.5 (3H, t, J 7.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, q, J 7.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 6.6 (1H, s, C₃-H), 6.8 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, C₆-H), 7.4 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, C₅-H); IR (KBr) : 895, 1360, 1520, 1740 cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 57.85; H, 4.40; N, 5.63. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁O₅N : C, 57.83; H, 4.41; N, 5.62%).

Fig. 1

Conclusions :

We used the claycop (copper nitrate impregnated on montmorillonite K10) as the nitration agent and aimed to achieve higher regioselectivity and increase the yields of nitro coumarins. The experiment results showed that the claycop method significantly increased both regioselective and yields. Coumarins are nitrated by claycop (cupric nitrate impregnated on the K10 montmorillonite) in acetic anhydride at room temperature to give corresponding regioselective mononitro coumarins in good to excellent yields. In addition, this procedure provided good yields under mild conditions and simple workup procedure. Hence it can be concluded that reaction offers an alternate better method for preparation of nitro coumarins and can be extended to other heterocyclic compounds as well.

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